

(60%, 10 ml) was kept at room temperature for 80 h. On acidification with dilute HCl, a solid was obtained which was extracted with ether (100 ml). The ethereal extract was washed with water and then concentrated to afford 4, then crystallising from ether-acetone mixture, (350 mg), m.p. 180–84°d; δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 14.00 (s, OH), 7.85 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, H- β), 7.65 (1H, d, *J* 16Hz, H- α) 7.60 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, *ortho*-coupled protons in B-ring), 7.30–7.40 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 6.92 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, *ortho*-coupled protons in B-ring), 6.05 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-3'), 5.95 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-5'), 5.19 (2H, d, CH₂Ph), 4.00 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.90 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

Compound 4 (250 mg) in amyl alcohol (15 ml) was treated with SeO₂ (250 mg) as usual⁵ and the product 6 crystallised from C₆H₆-petroleum ether mixture, (200 mg), m.p. 120–23°; δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-2' and 6'), 7.35–7.40 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-3' and 5'), 6.83 (1H, s, H-3), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 5.20 (2H, d, CH₂Ph) and 3.95 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

The flavone, 6 (150 mg) was dissolved in EtOAc (40 ml) and Pd-C (10%, 100 mg)^{7,8} was added. The mixture was stirred under H₂-atmosphere for 5 h. The catalyst was filtered, solvent removed and the product crystallised from MeOH-Me₂CO mixture as microcrystalline yellow substance (110 mg), m.p. 160–63°d; δ (d₆-DMSO, 90 MHz) 10.82 (s, OH), 7.90 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-2' and 6'), 7.0 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-3' and 5'), 6.35 (1H, s, H-3), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-8), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-6), 4.0 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.90 (3H, s, 1 × MeO). It was identical to the natural sample 1.

Synthesis of 2: 2,4-Di-*O*-methylphloroacetophenone (500 mg) and anisaldehyde (500 mg) in EtOH (20 ml) containing aqueous NaOH (60%; 15 ml) was kept at room temperature for 80 h, and worked up as usual. The chalcone (5) was crystallised from ether-benzene mixture, (400 mg), m.p. 140–42°; δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 14.0 (s, OH), 7.80 (1H, d, *J* 16Hz, H- β), 7.64 (1H, *J* 16Hz, H- α), 7.60 and 6.93 (2H each, both separate d, *J* 9Hz, *ortho*-coupled-H in B-ring), 6.03 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-3'), 5.94 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-5'), 4.0 (3H, s, 1 × MeO), 3.92 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.88 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

Compound 5 (300 mg) in amyl alcohol (20 ml) was treated with SeO₂ (310 mg) as usual and the product, 2 was crystallised from Me₂CO-Et₂O mixture as yellow crystals (220 mg), m.p. 162–63° (lit.⁹ 162–63°); δ (DMSO-d₆, 90 MHz) 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-2' and 6'), 6.82 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, H-3' and 5'), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 2.5Hz, H-8), 6.32 (1H, s, H-3), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 4.0 (3H, s, 1 × MeO), 3.97 (3H, s, 1 × MeO) and 3.92 (3H, s, 1 × MeO).

The compounds 1–6 gave satisfactory analytical data.

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Synthesis of some New 4-Methylcoumarins

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4-Methylcoumarins comprise of an important group of natural products. A few of them have been found to possess choleric¹, analgesic², antispermatogenic³ and diuretic⁴ properties. It has been observed¹ that coumarins carrying a 4-methyl function have much stronger choleric property than those lacking this functionality; furthermore, the metabolites of the former compounds were rapidly excreted while those of the latter compounds were slowly excreted. In view of these observations and better *in vivo* functioning and ease of excretion of their metabolites, we have carried out the synthesis of some new 4-methylcoumarins having (ethoxycarbonyl)methyl- and (ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl side chains at C-3 carbon atom via Pechmann reaction. 1,2,4-Trihydroxybenzene⁵ on condensation with α -acetyl diethyl succinate gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (1). This on complete methylation and acetylation gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-dimethoxycoumarin (2) and 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-diacetoxycoumarin (3), respecti-

vely. Similarly, 1,2,4-trihydroxybenzene on condensation with diethyl α -acetoglutarate gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (4) which on complete methylation and acetylation gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-6,7-dimethoxycoumarin (5) and 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-6,7-diacetoxycoumarin (6), respectively. 3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-5,7-dihydroxycoumarin (7) and 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-7,8-dihydroxycoumarin (10) were earlier prepared by Shah and Shah⁶ by using H_2SO_4 as the condensing agent, and the yields were 32 and 45%, respectively. We have modified the conditions and got better yields (62% for 7 and 50% for 10) by using $POCl_3$ and $ZnCl_2$ as the condensing agents. 3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-5,7-dihydroxycoumarin (7) on complete methylation and acetylation gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-5,7-dimethoxycoumarin (8) and 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-5,7-diacetoxycoumarin (9), whereas 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-7,8-dihydroxycoumarin (10) on methylation and acetylation gave 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (11) and 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-7,8-diacetoxycoumarin (12).

The biological screening of the compounds for their analgesic, diuretic, and antispermatogenic behaviour is under investigation.

1: $R = -CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = -OH$, $R_3 = -OH$, $R_4 = -H$; 2: $R = -CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -OCH_3$, $R_3 = -OCH_3$, $R_4 = -H$; 3: $R = -CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -OCOCH_3$, $R_3 = -OCOCH_3$, $R_4 = -H$; 4: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -OH$, $R_3 = -OH$, $R_4 = -H$; 5: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -OCH_3$, $R_3 = -OCH_3$, $R_4 = -H$; 6: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -OCOCH_3$, $R_3 = -OCOCH_3$, $R_4 = -H$; 7: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -OH$, $R_2 = -H$, $R_3 = -OH$, $R_4 = -H$; 8: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -OCH_3$, $R_2 = -H$, $R_3 = -OCH_3$, $R_4 = -H$; 9: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -OCOCH_3$, $R_2 = -H$, $R_3 = -OCOCH_3$, $R_4 = -H$; 10: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -H$, $R_3 = -OH$, $R_4 = -OH$; 11: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -H$, $R_3 = -OCH_3$, $R_4 = -OCH_3$; 12: $R = -CH_2CH_2COOEt$, $R_1 = -H$, $R_2 = -H$, $R_3 = -OCOCH_3$, $R_4 = -OCOCH_3$.

Experimental

Unless stated otherwise all melting points were taken in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Silica gel was used for tlc. Uv spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 554 spectrophotometer. Ir spectra were measured using KBr disc on a Shimadzu 535 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer.

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (1): To a mixture of 1,2,4-trihydroxybenzene (2.12 g) and $POCl_3$ (1.5 ml), α -acetyl diethyl succinate (3.24 g) was added and the contents were continuously stirred at room temperature for 24 h

under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was taken up in ether and the ether layer washed with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Concentration of ether solution yielded a solid which was crystallised from methanol as white crystals (1, 2.5 g), m.p. 205–07°. λ_{max} (MeOH) 344, 292 and 216 nm; ν_{max} 3400, 2918, 1720, 1660, 1615, 1527, 1420, 1366, 1325, 1285, 1209, 1185, 1154, 1096, 1018, 902, 860, 840, 785 and 768 cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.19 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 2.28 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 3.58 (2H, s, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 4.06 (2H, q, J 7Hz, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 6.71 (1H, s, C-5H) and 7.05 (1H, s, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-dimethoxycoumarin (2): Compound 1 (500 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (15 ml) and to it ignited K_2CO_3 (4 g) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml) were added, and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The solid obtained after working up the reaction was crystallised from methanol as white crystals (2; 600 mg), m.p. 128–29°. λ_{max} (MeOH) 336, 286 and 227 nm; ν_{max} 2950, 1733, 1632, 1415, 1340, 1195, 1168, 1102, 1085, 1052, 1040, 999, 975, 884, 850 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.21 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 2.34 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 3.67 (2H, s, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 3.90 (6H, s, $2 \times OCH_3$), 4.14 (2H, q, J 7Hz, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 6.78 (1H, s, C-5H) and 6.95 (1H, s, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)methyl-4-methyl-6,7-diacetoxycoumarin (3): Compound 1 (500 mg) was dissolved in dry pyridine (5 ml) and to it was added dry acetic anhydride (4 ml), and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. After working up the reaction, the solid obtained was crystallised from chloroform–petrol as colourless crystals (3; 550 mg), m.p. 135–36°. δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.28 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 2.32 (6H, s, $2 \times OCOCH_3$), 2.38 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 3.74 (2H, s, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 4.17 (2H, q, J 7Hz, $CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 7.22 (1H, s, C-5H) and 7.46 (1H, s, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (4): To a mixture of 1,2,4-trihydroxybenzene (2 g) and $POCl_3$ (2.1 ml), diethyl α -acetoglutarate (4 ml) were added and the reaction mixture stirred under nitrogen for 24 h. The solid obtained after work up as under (1), was crystallised from methanol as a brownish solid (4; 2 g), m.p. 191–93°. λ_{max} (MeOH) 346, 292 and 226 nm; ν_{max} 3400, 1720, 1646, 1570, 1448, 1422, 1375, 1343, 1325, 1285, 1238, 1205, 1114, 1030, 940, 905 and 895 cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.16 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $CH_2CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 2.28 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.48 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 2.75 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 4.00 (2H, q, J 7Hz, $CH_2CH_2COOCH_2CH_3$), 6.61 (1H, s, C-5H) and 6.90 (1H, s, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-6,7-dimethoxycoumarin (5): Compound 4 (500 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (15 ml), and to it ignited K_2CO_3 (5 g) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml) were added,

and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The solid obtained after working up the reaction mixture was crystallised from methanol as white needles (5; 550 mg), m.p. 132–33°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 332, 292 and 224 nm; ν_{max} 1730, 1690, 1615, 1570, 1505, 1461, 1440, 1408, 1395, 1270, 1248, 1205, 1190, 1160, 1070, 1035, 1005, 900, 845 and 830 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.21 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.38 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.60 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.85 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.88 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 4.02 (2H, q, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 6.70 (1H, s, C-5H) and 6.88 (1H, s, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-6,7-diacetoxycoumarin (6): Compound 4 (500 mg) was dissolved in dry pyridine (3 ml) and dry acetic anhydride (4 ml) was added and the mixture was then stirred for 12 h. The product was crystallised from chloroform-petrol as light pink crystals (6; 500 mg), m.p. 113–14°; δ (CDCl_3) 1.21 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.28 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 2.37 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.60 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.90 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.05 (2H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 7.11 (1H, s, C-5H) and 7.35 (1H, s, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-5,7-dihydroxycoumarin (7): A mixture of phloroglucinol (2 g), POCl_3 (2.1 ml), ZnCl_2 (1 g) and diethyl α -acetoglutamate (4 ml) was stirred for 12 h. The solid obtained after work up as under (1) was crystallised from methanol as brownish solid (7; 2.5 g), m.p. 220–21°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 324, 260 and 220 nm; ν_{max} 3360, 1705, 1665, 1595, 1555, 1462, 1385, 1366, 1286, 1162, 1130, 1096, 1040, 850, 805, 780 and 740 cm^{-1} ; δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 1.20 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.50 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.65 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.78 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.00 (2H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 6.00 (1H, d, J 2Hz, C-6H) and 6.15 (1H, d, J 2Hz, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-5,7-dimethoxycoumarin (8): Compound 7 (500 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (15 ml), and to it ignited K_2CO_3 (5 g) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 14 h and the solid obtained after the usual work up was crystallised from methanol as light brown crystals (8; 500 mg), m.p. 94–95°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 328, 264, 230 nm; ν_{max} 2960, 1725, 1690, 1615, 1595, 1460, 1420, 1385, 1376, 1302, 1270, 1210, 1160, 1131, 1095, 1065, 832, 780 and 740 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.20 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.50 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.60 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.75 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.10 (2H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 6.35 (1H, d, J 2Hz, C-6H) and 6.45 (1H, d, J 2Hz, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-5,7-diacetoxycoumarin (9): Compound 7 (500 mg) was acetylated with dry pyridine (4 ml) and dry acetic

anhydride (5 ml); the diacetate (9) was crystallised from chloroform-petrol as white crystals (9; 500 mg), m.p. 105–06°; δ (CDCl_3) 1.18 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.30 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 2.37 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 2.52 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.60 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.88 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.10 (2H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2Hz, C-6H) and 7.00 (1H, d, J 2Hz, C-8H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-7,8-dihydroxycoumarin (10): A mixture of pyrogallol (2.0 g), POCl_3 (2.1 ml), ZnCl_2 (1 g) and diethyl α -acetoglutamate (4 ml) was stirred for 6 h. The solid obtained after working up the reaction as under (1), was crystallised from methanol as white needles (10; 2.0 g), m.p. 158–59°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 324, 240 and 224 nm; ν_{max} 3420, 2940, 1730, 1685, 1605, 1500, 1460, 1430, 1365, 1295, 1195, 1166, 1124, 1030, 915, 855, 800 and 780 cm^{-1} ; δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 1.18 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.32 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.52 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.75 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.00 (2H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 6.65 (1H, d, J 9Hz, C-6H), and 6.90 (1H, d, J 9Hz, C-5H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (11): Compound 10 (500 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (20 ml) and to it ignited K_2CO_3 (6g) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 5 h and solid obtained after usual work up was crystallised from methanol as white crystals (11; 500 mg), m.p. 90–91°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 320, 266 and 220 nm; ν_{max} 2980, 1685, 1070, 1615, 1580, 1505, 1440, 1375, 1340, 1320, 1260, 1180, 1155, 1085, 1032, 910, 840, 812, 800, 780 and 765 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.20 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.40 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.58 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.86 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.90 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 4.02 (2H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 6.78 (1H, d, J 9Hz, C-6H) and 7.24 (1H, d, J 9Hz, C-5H).

3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl-4-methyl-7,8-diacetoxycoumarin (12): Compound 10 (500 mg) was acetylated with dry pyridine (4 ml) and dry acetic anhydride (4 ml). The solid obtained after working up the reaction was crystallised from chloroform-petrol as white solid (12; 500 mg), m.p. 114–15°; δ (CDCl_3) 1.21 (3H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.32 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 2.40 (3H, s, C-4- CH_3), 2.60 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.90 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.05 (2H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 7.10 (1H, d, J 9Hz, C-6H) and 7.45 (1H, d, J 9Hz, C-5H).

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Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Study on some 4-Methoxyacetophenones

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THE study of the electrical dipole moment of certain anisoles and thioanisoles led to the discovery of a new effect termed steric enhancement of resonance¹ (SER). Many papers based on physicochemical properties of suitably substituted anisoles and thioanisoles were published² providing evidence for the aforesaid effect. We have recorded and analysed the pmr data of some alkyl- and halogeno-methoxyacetophenones to gain evidence for the newly observed effect.

All the compounds described in Table 1 were prepared by known standard procedures.

Nmr chemical shifts have been extensively used as probes of electronic substituent effects^{3,4}. Heathcock⁵ has analysed the influence of the substituents on the chemical shifts of the alkoxy hydrogen of anisoles and phenetoles. The data indicate that in *ortho*-substituted-anisoles the methoxyl protons have higher chemical shift values (downfield) than those of the corresponding *para*-substituted-anisoles, irrespective of whether the substituent is electron-donor or electron-acceptor. This can be explained on the basis of SER.

The pmr data on some methoxyacetophenones are recorded and presented in Table 1. We have analysed the sensitivity of methoxyl hydrogen and acetyl hydrogen shieldings to substitution in aromatic ring. It is found that the methoxyl hydrogen resonance is not significantly affected when further substitution takes place either in 3-position or in 3- and 5-positions of 4-methoxyacetophenone eventhough the value changes when we go from anisole to 4-methoxyacetophenone. Similarly, all the compounds studied have more or less the same chemical shift values for the acetyl group. Therefore, we failed to get any useful information about the operation of ser from the above analysis on pmr data.

However, there is a recent report by Ganapathy and Ramanujam⁶ on the pmr spectral data of the compounds of interest, in which they claimed that the acetyl proton shift in the compounds furnishes evidence for SER. Their data are also presented in parenthesis in Table 1. The assignment of the signal for acetyl proton by the above authors of the compound 4-methoxy-3-methylacetophenone seems to be erroneous. They have assigned the signal at δ 2.0 to methyl proton of the acetyl group and δ 2.5 to the 3-methyl group, we feel that it might be the other way. We assigned the peak at δ 2.52 to methyl of acetyl group and at δ 2.23 to the 3-methyl group. When we compare the monosubstituted- and trisubstituted-acetophenones, it is obvious that acetyl group should have value approximately δ 2.5. Moreover, it is claimed that the chemical shift of acetyl group value gradually decreases from 3-fluoro- to 3-bromo- to 3-iodo-4-methoxyacetophenone. However, in our determination we obtained almost the same values (Table 1) and a decreasing trend has not been observed. The values we got are more reliable because they have been taken from the computer print-out of the nmr machine (JEOL FX Q90). It is concluded from our observations that the substituent chemical shift either on acetyl proton or methoxyl proton is not that much sensitive to realise the new effect. We fail to understand why the chemical shift values for the acetyl methyls and the aryl methyl (in one case) of the different compounds, as observed by us, differ so much from those reported by Ganapathy and Ramanujam⁶.

TABLE 1—PMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) OF SOME ACETOPHENONES*

Acetophenones	Methoxyl	Acetyl-methyl	Aryl-methyl
Acetophenone	—	2.6 (2.5)	—
4-Methoxy	3.92 (3.8)	2.51 (2.4)	—
4-Methoxy-3-methyl	3.86 (3.8)	2.52 (2.0)	2.23 (2.5)
3-Fluoro-4-methoxy	3.92 (4.0)	2.51 (2.2)	—
3-Chloro-4-methoxy	3.94 (4.0)	2.53 (2.1)	—
3-Bromo-4-methoxy	3.92 (4.0)	2.51 (2.0)	—
3-Iodo-4-methoxy	3.95 (3.9)	2.55 (1.8)	—
4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethyl	3.74 (3.8)	2.50 (2.6)	2.29 (2.7)
3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxy	3.98 (4.0)	2.58 (2.6)	—
3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxy	3.99 (4.0)	2.58 (2.6)	—

*Values in parentheses from Ref. 6.